

A Study on the Ecological Translation of Zhaoqing Tourism Slogans in the Context of Holistic Tourism — Insights from Tourism Slogans in Selected U.S. States

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Abstract: Holistic tourism is currently flourishing across China. Given the insufficiency or inaccuracies in the translation of Chinese tourism slogans in certain domestic areas, this study applies the three-dimensional principles of eco-translatology—focusing on linguistic, cultural, and communicative aspects. Starting with insights derived from English tourism slogans in select U.S. states, this study explores the translation of holistic tourism slogans in Chinese, using representative slogans from Zhaoqing as case studies. The goal is to enhance the international promotion of tourism slogans for cities, assisting tourism destinations in reaching a global audience.

Keywords: Holistic tourism; Slogans; Eco-translatology; Three-dimensional principles.

I. INTRODUCTION

The concept of holistic tourism was first proposed in 2013 by scholars Lü Junfang, Li Xinjian, and others, referring to the comprehensive optimization and integration of all tourism resources within a given area. This approach aims to facilitate deep integration between tourism and other industries to achieve resource sharing and complementary advantages in a holistic tourism system (Lü, 2013). This concept seeks to establish an “all-encompassing” tourism destination, breaking down traditional boundaries of specific scenic spots so that tourists can experience a rich blend of natural landscapes, historical and cultural heritage, and modern urban attractions within a single area (Li, Zhang, & Cui, 2013). In 2017, holistic tourism was formally elevated to a national strategy in China, becoming a significant part of the government’s annual work report, underscoring its strategic importance to national economic and social development. Consequently, governments across China have launched related policies and plans for holistic tourism, aimed at boosting local economic vitality, increasing employment opportunities, and enhancing residents’ quality of life. This has spurred vigorous development of holistic tourism across multiple provinces and cities, promoting resource integration and fostering diverse developmental models.

Zhaoqing City, located in southern China and rich in historical and cultural resources as well as unique natural landscapes, has found that traditional tourism methods no longer satisfy visitors’ demand for diverse, high-quality experiences amid rapid economic growth and rising living standards. To adapt to this trend, Zhaoqing City introduced the “Attracting Visitors to Zhaoqing” tourism marketing initiative within the *Zhaoqing Holistic Tourism Development Master Plan (2019–2025)*, aiming to comprehensively enhance tourism quality and establish a holistic tourism system. This plan emphasizes promoting the city by combining natural landscapes—such as mountains, lakes, urban areas, and rivers—with historical and cultural attractions. Furthermore, with support from key media at the central, provincial, and international

levels, Zhaoqing actively promotes its unique features, such as the magnificent “Big Dipper” and the traditional Duanyan inkstone culture, striving to create a city brand under the slogan “Capital of Inkstones, Starlike Zhaoqing.” To propel Zhaoqing into the international market and elevate its global reputation, the precise translation of tourism slogans is crucial (Zhaoqing Municipal Government, 2020, p. 138). However, Zhaoqing currently faces numerous challenges in translating its tourism slogans, primarily due to most slogans being available only in Chinese, with few versions in English or other languages. Additionally, some existing English translations suffer from quality issues, significantly diminishing their communicative effectiveness. Given this, the present study employs the eco-translatology perspective to analyze the translation of tourism slogans from select U.S. states and extract useful insights to inform the translation practices of Zhaoqing's tourism slogans, ultimately supporting the international promotion of its holistic tourism.

II. OVERVIEW OF ECO-TRANSLATOLOGY

Eco-translatology, proposed by Hu Gengshen, is an interdisciplinary translation theory that emphasizes the dynamic interactions among the translator, text, and environment. It explores how translation activities achieve a balance among various ecological elements. Specifically, eco-translatology focuses on the interrelation and interactions within three dimensions: translation ecology (the context of translation), textual ecology (the translated text), and translator community ecology. Within this framework, translation ecology refers to the bidirectional connections and interactions that a translator maintains with both internal and external environments. Broadly defined, the translation ecological environment encompasses all external conditions that impact the translator's ability to perform and develop. These conditions include various social, political, economic, cultural, and linguistic factors, all of which play a critical role in influencing the conduct, effectiveness, and reception of translation activities.

In eco-translatology, the term "subject" is not limited to an individual translator; rather, it refers to all entities and organizations involved in the translation process. Hu Gengshen describes this collective as the "translator community," which includes sponsors, authors, translators, readers, editors, publishers, and marketers. The external environment surrounding this community is equally complex, encompassing social, political, economic, natural, and cultural linguistic contexts that are either directly or indirectly associated with translation activities. More specifically, the translation ecological environment consists of a network of interwoven elements that together form the essential conditions for translation to take place, develop, and persist. These conditions encompass human factors, such as the readership's acceptance of the translated content and the local culture's validation of the text, as well as natural factors like communication technologies, publishing resources, and the ease of cross-linguistic interaction. In this sense, the translation environment and the translation ecology form an organic whole, mutually dependent and influential, ultimately determining the quality and effectiveness of the translation (Hu, 2016).

Hu Gengshen further refined the theoretical structure of eco-translatology into nine core research foci and theoretical perspectives: (1) translation ecological environment, (2) ecological paradigm, (3) ecological rationality, (4) associative chains, (5) translation as action, (6) translator-centeredness, (7) adaptation/selection, (8) “three-dimensional” transformations, and (9) post-translation accountability (Hu, 2016). These theoretical perspectives create a systematic analytical framework for examining ecological factors within the translation process. Among these, the translation ecological environment pertains to the external setting of translation activities, while the ecological paradigm emphasizes the organic linkage between translation and the broader ecosystem, positing “translation as adaptation and selection” as a core concept. Ecological rationality focuses on the rational decisions made in translation, examining how translators achieve balanced decisions within different temporal and cultural contexts. The associative chains perspective highlights the relationships and interactions among various elements in the translation process, enabling translators to better understand the multifaceted relationship between the source text and the target text.

Among these nine perspectives, the "three-dimensional" transformation is particularly noteworthy as a concrete translation approach that emphasizes the integrated application of linguistic, cultural, and communicative dimensions. The linguistic dimension encompasses the rhetorical features of the text, focusing on preserving the original style, rhythm, and linguistic characteristics in translation. The cultural dimension pertains to conveying cultural connotations, considering the receptivity of diverse cultural backgrounds and their respective differences. The communicative dimension highlights the effective transmission of information in the target text, ensuring that the translation achieves smooth communication within the cultural context of the target audience. These three dimensions provide clear operational guidance for

translators, enabling a more comprehensive approach to address the complexity and diversity inherent in translation activities. In this study on tourism slogan translation, the "three-dimensional" transformation method will serve as the framework for analyzing Zhaoqing's tourism slogans from the linguistic, cultural, and communicative perspectives through an eco-translatology lens.

Domestic and international scholars have made significant advances in the study of eco-translatology, spanning theoretical frameworks, methodological applications, and interdisciplinary integration. Foundational work by Hu Gengshen and others established the basic theoretical structure of eco-translatology, defining it as a translation perspective concerned with the "translation ecological environment" and "translation adaptability," and introducing the three-dimensional principles of language, culture, and communication (Hu, 2016). Building on this foundation, various studies have further explored specific applications of eco-translatology and the implementation of adaptive choices. Domestic scholars such as Zhu Wentao and Cai Ying have expanded on eco-translatology from multiple angles, arguing that translation activities are not simply linguistic conversions but involve a balanced interaction of language, culture, and social information within a diverse ecology. They propose "adaptation" and "balance" in translation activities to maintain dynamic stability within the translation ecology (Hu, 2016). Additionally, Wang Yunfang (2021) proposed the concept of "translator-centeredness" within the eco-translatology framework, emphasizing the ecological role of the translator. This role not only involves attention to the quality and accuracy of the translation but also considers the adaptability and acceptance of the translated text within the target culture.

Internationally, scholars such as Newmark and Hurtado Albir have also examined the value of eco-translatology in cross-cultural communication. Newmark advocates for "functional equivalence" in translation, adjusting the translation according to the cultural acceptance practices of the target language to achieve functional ecological balance. Hurtado Albir and others, from a translation pedagogy perspective, explored how eco-translatology methods can enhance students' cross-cultural communication skills, suggesting that translators should not only focus on linguistic conversion but also consider the cultural background and cognitive habits of target-language readers (Tao, 2014). In applied research, scholars have gradually implemented eco-translatology principles in specific case studies, such as tourism text translation, legal text translation, and commercial text translation. Research outcomes indicate that eco-translatology offers strong guidance and practicality in these fields. In the tourism text domain, Lai Xiaoqin (2019) noted that tourism slogans, as an important means of cultural promotion, require translation that carefully considers the cultural symbols of the source text and the psychological responses of the target audience, ensuring that the slogans carry cultural resonance within the target language environment, thus better fulfilling the purpose of tourism promotion. Overall, existing literature widely agrees that eco-translatology significantly enhances cross-cultural communication, increases the adaptability and communicative power of translations, and that applying eco-translatology principles to tourism slogan translation can improve the international transmission of a city's cultural image.

III. THREE-DIMENSIONAL ANALYSIS AND INSIGHTS FROM TOURISM SLOGANS IN SELECT U.S. STATES

To promote tourism development, U.S. states commonly craft tourism slogans that reflect local characteristics. These slogans often center on natural landscapes, historical backgrounds, or cultural features of each state, employing concise, engaging, and memorable phrases to attract potential tourists. Many of these slogans are printed directly on license plates, accompanied by the state name and representative symbols, serving as highly recognizable "moving advertisements." Beyond mere promotion, these slogans also convey regional culture, encapsulating the unique essence of each locality. From the perspective of eco-translatology, translating tourism slogans requires consideration of three key elements: linguistic, cultural, and communicative dimensions. These aspects ensure that the translation conveys the cultural essence of the destination while being easily understood by the target audience. The following section categorizes and analyzes the tourism slogans of several U.S. states based on eco-translatology's three-dimensional principles to provide insights for translating Chinese tourism slogans.

A. Insights into Slogan Translation from a Three-Dimensional Perspective

To comprehensively explore the application of eco-translatology in tourism slogan translation, this section analyzes each of the three principles: linguistic, cultural, and communicative. In essence, slogan translation should not only focus on simplicity and rhythm but also consider the adaptability to cultural backgrounds and accuracy in information

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transmission. This multi-dimensional perspective helps achieve ecological balance in translation, supporting Zhaoqing's holistic tourism slogans in enhancing their communicative power and appeal in international promotion.

(1). Linguistic/Rhetorical Dimension

Acronym and Wordplay Techniques: Slogans in this dimension often employ acronym play, making use of phonetic similarities, alliteration, and assonance within place names. This abstract and figurative approach to information conveyance helps visitors emotionally connect with the distinct characteristics of the destination, as shown in the following examples:

Balti-More Than You Can See: This slogan creatively uses the word "More" within "Baltimore", emphasizing the depth of experiences the city offers. **Colorado – Colorful Colorado:** The repetition of "Color" at the beginning of both words forms alliteration, creating a catchy phrase that reflects the vibrant scenery of the state.

Abstract and Concrete Combination Techniques: In this approach, slogans often employ parallel structures to either highlight a notable landmark or provide a highly abstract summary of visitor experiences. Examples include:

South Dakota – Great Faces, Great Places: This slogan points to a well-known attraction, the Mount Rushmore National Memorial, and uses repetition of "Great" and rhyming between "faces" and "places" to enhance memorability and create a parallel structure. **Alaska – Beyond Your Dreams. Within Your Reach:** The words "beyond" and "within" form an antithetical contrast, using a parallel structure to abstractly summarize the allure and accessibility of Alaska.

(2). Communicative Dimension

Slogans in this dimension approach translation from the perspective of the tourist's experience, emphasizing contrast and highlighting key characteristics that each state aims to convey to visitors. This style aligns the communicative intent of the slogan with the tourist's experience of the destination. These slogans are generally abstract, often appearing as single sentences or phrases and sometimes utilizing hyperbole. For instance:

Wyoming – Like No Place on Earth: Wyoming is known for its rich tourism resources, stunning landscapes, and deep historical and cultural roots, with Yellowstone National Park being one of its most iconic sites. However, instead of listing specific attractions, this slogan focuses on capturing the unique visitor experience of Wyoming.

(3). Cultural Dimension

Slogans in this dimension highlight a representative landmark or cultural feature, typically using descriptive words or phrases. These slogans are straightforward, factual, and easy to understand, directly pointing to the destination's natural or cultural highlights. Examples include:

Historical or Cultural References:

North Carolina – First in Flight: This slogan references the Wright brothers' achievement of the first successful flight in 1903 in North Carolina.

Hawaii – The Islands of Aloha: "Aloha" is a Hawaiian word meaning "hello" or "welcome," which Hawaiian natives often say to greet guests, emphasizing the indigenous culture of Hawaii.

Local Products or Natural Landmarks:

Michigan – Auto State: Michigan is known as the largest center of automobile manufacturing in the U.S.

Minnesota – 10,000 Lakes: Minnesota has over 15,000 lakes, earning it the nickname "Land of 10,000 Lakes."

B. Insights for Translating Zhaoqing's Tourism Slogans from U.S. State Slogans

The following translation principles can be derived from the analysis of tourism slogans from U.S. states and serve as guidelines for translating Zhaoqing's holistic tourism slogans into English:

- (1). Each slogan should focus on a single representative landmark or feature.
- (2). Multiple slogans could be used concurrently across different contexts.

- (3). In slogans using a parallel structure, the first phrase should reference the landmark, while the second focuses on the visitor experience.
- (4). If the original slogan's landmarks are unclear or too numerous, adopt an abstract perspective that centers on visitor experience.
- (5). Use simple and commonly understood words, avoiding complex or uncommon terms.
- (6). Avoid using transliterated names for landmarks and figures when the original meaning may not be apparent to English-speaking audiences.

IV. ECOLOGICAL TRANSLATION ANALYSIS OF ZHAOQING'S TOURISM SLOGANS

To gain a deeper understanding of the ecological translation practices for Zhaoqing's tourism slogans, it is essential to apply eco-translatology's theoretical framework to systematically analyze the existing translations of these slogans. By employing the three-dimensional principles of linguistic, cultural, and communicative perspectives, the analysis can uncover challenges and deficiencies encountered during the translation process. Additionally, it can explore optimization strategies to enhance the effectiveness of cross-cultural communication. This section will conduct a detailed analysis of specific examples of Zhaoqing's slogans from an ecological translation perspective, offering practical guidance for the future international promotion of these slogans.

A. Current Status and Challenges of Zhaoqing's Tourism Slogans

In analyzing nine representative tourism slogans from the entire Zhaoqing area—including the city and its subordinate districts and counties—through the lens of eco-translatology and insights from U.S. state tourism slogans, several distinctive features of Zhaoqing's Chinese tourism slogans become evident. Compared to U.S. state slogans, Zhaoqing's slogans display unique characteristics in rhetoric, content, and expressive style. First, many of Zhaoqing's slogans employ parallel rhetorical structures with balanced phrasing and symmetrical word counts, creating a beauty reminiscent of traditional Chinese poetry. This structure is common in Chinese, as it enhances rhythm and makes slogans more memorable, while also reflecting the cultural depth of the region. However, parallelism poses challenges in translation, as this structure is less prevalent in English, where sentence structures and rhythm can vary significantly from Chinese.

Additionally, Zhaoqing's slogans often contain strong local cultural elements, emphasizing long-standing history and rich cultural heritage, which are evident in word choice and expression. For example, place names are frequently combined with culturally significant terms, highlighting the region's cultural identity. However, this method of integrating place names within slogans may lose its contextual cultural significance when translated into English. Therefore, translations should consider using equivalent words or cultural analogues to convey deeper meanings effectively.

Moreover, Zhaoqing's slogans prominently feature place names, with most slogans directly incorporating them to underscore regional identity and local characteristics. However, this approach presents limitations in English translation, as transliterations of place names may fail to resonate with English-speaking readers or convey specific cultural or geographical meanings. Unlike certain U.S. state slogans, Zhaoqing's slogans have not fully exploited the semantic or phonetic potential of place names to enhance slogan appeal. For instance, Maryland's slogan "Balti-More Than You Can See" cleverly plays on the word "More" within "Baltimore", adding layers of meaning and interest. Similar techniques are not yet evident in Zhaoqing's slogans.

It is also noteworthy that some of Zhaoqing's tourism slogans lack distinctiveness, failing to highlight local features or cultural uniqueness. Some slogans attempt to encompass multiple scenic elements within a single phrase to capture as many attractions as possible. However, this information-dense approach complicates the slogan's focus, reducing its impact. Given the necessity for conciseness in English slogans, directly translating these dense slogans into English may lead to an overload of information, which hinders memorability. Tao Xiaoting suggests that a city or tourist area can create multiple slogans to meet diverse market or visitor needs, each reflecting different features and strengths (Tao, 2014). For example, Beijing uses 13 different slogans in various promotional contexts. A similar approach could enhance the adaptability and effectiveness of Zhaoqing's slogans.

For international markets, tourism cities can also combine short-term and long-term slogans to incrementally build a destination's brand image, gradually reinforcing its identity at different stages of promotion. This strategy mirrors the approach taken by some U.S. states, where dozens of different slogans are available, allowing for flexibility and

adaptability to diverse market demands and promotional contexts. This diversified, phased approach could significantly improve the adaptability and communicative effectiveness of Zhaoqing's tourism slogans in various cultural markets.

B. Analysis of Representative Slogan Translations

This section analyzes the translations of nine representative tourism slogans from Zhaoqing, applying the three-dimensional principles of eco-translatology—namely, the linguistic, cultural, and communicative dimensions. These principles help optimize the direction of slogan translation, ensuring that the translations not only preserve the cultural essence of the original text but also achieve effective information transmission and aesthetic appeal in English.

Slogan: 中国砚都·七星肇庆 (Zhaoqing City)

Translations:

- (1). Home of Fine Inkstones
- (2). A City Amidst Seven Stars
- (3). Countryside Paradise
- (4). Starlike Zhaoqing, Capital of Inkstones

Analysis:

From the communicative dimension, the original slogan contains four key elements: "China", "Inkstone Capital", "Seven-Star Rock", and "Zhaoqing." The Chinese slogan is highly compact, and attempting to translate each component directly would not align with the succinct nature of English slogans and could lead to cultural confusion. Thus, a reduction strategy is preferable. Translations (1) and (2) each emphasize a single cultural element from the original, making them clear and attractive to international tourists with varying interests. Linguistically, both translations use short phrases that are easy to remember.

Translation (3) shifts away from the two specific landmarks, instead encapsulating Zhaoqing's essence as a city known for its scenic landscapes. The term "paradise" is familiar to foreign visitors and evokes a strong, emotive response, thus enhancing the communicative dimension.

Translation (4) combines the natural and cultural features of the original slogan by using "Zhaoqing" as the focal term, retaining its phonetic form to preserve its exotic cultural resonance. This slogan aligns with Zhaoqing's holistic tourism strategy and cultural promotion, aiming to highlight the city's name for international recognition. The term "Starlike" subtly captures the essence of "Seven-Star Rock" without directly translating it, making the phrase shorter and more aesthetically pleasing in English.

Overall, each translation leverages different aspects of the original, with variations that target different dimensions (linguistic, cultural, and communicative) to enhance cross-cultural effectiveness and align with eco-translatology principles.

Slogan: 古端州 新活力 (Duanzhou District)

Translations:

- (1). Revitalize Duanzhou
- (2). Ancient Duanzhou, Revitalized Life

Analysis:

Historically known as Duanzhou, Zhaoqing has a deep-rooted past. Duanzhou was an ancient administrative region whose territory approximately corresponds to present-day Zhaoqing and parts of Yunfu City in Guangdong, dating back to the Qin dynasty when it was part of the Nanhai Commandery. From the communicative perspective, this slogan aligns with one of Zhaoqing's major objectives in the city's 14th Five-Year Plan, which includes urban renewal of Duanzhou's central district, aiming to create a high-quality, livable, and vibrant city. This project also seeks to restore the historical ambiance of Zhaoqing as a political, economic, and cultural hub of South China, establishing a unique Lingnan cultural landmark in the Greater Bay Area.

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From an eco-translatology perspective, the Chinese slogan aims to convey an aspiration similar to “national rejuvenation”, focusing on development and renewal. Rhetorically, the original slogan employs parallelism, contrasting “Ancient” and “New.” Thus, a reduction strategy is used in translation to simplify and convey the core intent effectively.

Translation (1) adopts a straightforward approach with “Revitalize Duanzhou”, capturing the essence of the city’s renewal goals. This option works well as a slogan, particularly in short-term marketing contexts.

Translation (2) can serve as a longer-term slogan, reflecting both Duanzhou’s historical heritage and its revitalization. The added word “Life” in this translation highlights the vibrancy of the community, suggesting that Duanzhou is thriving. The use of contrasting adjectives maintains the parallelism and mirrors the original slogan’s style, fulfilling both linguistic and communicative requirements.

Slogan: 湾区绿洲 “醉氧”鼎湖 (Dinghu District)

Translations:

- (1). So Good to Breathe
- (2). It’s Good to Breathe, Better to Breathe Freely, and Best to Breathe Freshly.
- (3). Forest Oxygen Bar, GBA Green Star

Analysis:

The original slogan includes multiple elements, such as the “Greater Bay Area (GBA)”, “oasis”, “negative ions”, and “Dinghu Mountain.” Given the density of information, a direct translation would obscure the message. To ensure clarity, the focus is shifted to key points that resonate with potential visitors, emphasizing the experience of breathing fresh air. Translation (1) simplifies the message, using a reduction strategy and focusing on the visitor experience. The phrase mirrors the style of experience-oriented U.S. state slogans.

Translation (2) utilizes contrast by playing on the positive degrees of “good”, “better”, and “best” to underscore the high oxygen quality of Dinghu Mountain, where the concentration of negative ions is the highest in the country. Translation (3) takes a more interpretive approach, using parallelism with “Bar” and “Star” to capture the essence of Dinghu Mountain’s “forest oxygen bar.” Additionally, this version incorporates “GBA” to align with Dinghu’s positioning in the Greater Bay Area, which meets the requirements of Zhaoqing’s external affairs department. This translation integrates both the cultural and communicative dimensions effectively, fulfilling eco-translatology’s principles by highlighting Dinghu’s unique natural and regional value.

Slogan: 千年古郡 人文高要 (Gaoyao District)

Translations:

- (1). Millennia Gaoyao
- (2). It’s That Old

Analysis:

This slogan highlights Gaoyao’s ancient history, with numerous historic villages such as Licha Bagua Village, Lian Tang Lychee Village, and Hui Long Chenghu Village, making it a valuable destination for those interested in cultural heritage. The focus is on the visitor experience and the slogan’s communicative function. Since “ancient” and “cultural richness” are inherently linked, a reduction strategy is employed, selecting only one aspect to emphasize.

Translation (1), “Millennia Gaoyao”, specifically addresses the historical aspect, emphasizing the long-standing history of Gaoyao.

Translation (2) takes inspiration from certain U.S. state slogans, approaching it from the tourist’s perspective with a conversational tone, suggesting the deep-rooted history through an informal expression. Both translations emphasize the communicative dimension and encourage curiosity about Gaoyao’s rich past.

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Slogan: 桔红玉翠 古邑四会 (Sihui City)

Translations:

- (1). Jade World, Dazzling World
- (2). Great Orange, Tasty Destination

Analysis:

This slogan's original Chinese phrase consists of four distinct elements—"orange", "jade", "ancient city", and "Sihui"—making it overly dense for a direct translation. Using a reduction approach, each translation highlights one prominent feature to maintain simplicity and clarity.

Translation (1), "Jade World, Dazzling World", focuses on Sihui's reputation for jade and gemstone craftsmanship. The repetition of "world" in a parallel structure emphasizes the abundance and appeal of these products, creating an immersive experience for potential visitors.

Translation (2), "Great Orange, Tasty Destination", highlights Sihui's renowned citrus produce, particularly the Shatang Orange. The use of "Great" and "Tasty" reflects U.S. state slogan styles, drawing on adjectives that carry positive connotations and cater to the visitor's experience. Both translations adopt the communicative dimension, focusing on specific attractions while preserving the original's appeal and functionality.

Slogan: 山水竹乡 魅力广宁 (Guangning County)

Translation: Great Bamboo, Great Place

Analysis:

From the communicative perspective, this slogan contains five elements—"mountain", "water", "bamboo", "countryside", and "Guangning"—which creates a dense message lacking a specific focal point. Given the compressed nature of Chinese slogans, a direct translation would not capture the intended effect in English. Therefore, a reduction approach is used, highlighting the most famous feature: "bamboo", specifically the "Guangning Bamboo Sea", which reflects Guangning's cultural identity. The phrase mirrors the style of U.S. state slogans by using parallel structure and repeating the word "Great" to reinforce Guangning's reputation for bamboo and bamboo products, fulfilling the communicative purpose effectively.

Slogan: 龙母故乡 崇德之城 (Deqing County)

Translation: Where There Is a Legend of Dragon Mother

Analysis:

This translation employs reduction, focusing solely on Deqing's most well-known cultural landmark, the "Dragon Mother", emphasizing the cultural dimension to serve the communicative intent. The more abstract Confucian concept of "revering virtue" is omitted to avoid ambiguity for foreign audiences, concentrating instead on the universally appealing legend of the Dragon Mother, which is more engaging for tourists. This approach preserves key cultural elements and allows visitors to intuitively connect with traditional values through the story of the Dragon Mother. Structurally, the slogan adopts the common English slogan form "Where +" to maintain the original's parallelism, achieving a balanced and culturally resonant translation.

Slogan: 岭南古都 秀美封开 (Fengkai County)

Translations:

- (1). With Prehistory Civilization
- (2). With Asia's Largest Rock
- (3). With China's Ayers Rock

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Analysis:

Fengkai is historically significant as one of the earliest inhabited areas in Lingnan and was once the political, economic, and cultural center of the Lingnan region, as well as the origin of Lingnan culture and Cantonese dialect. Translation (1) employs reduction, focusing on the “ancient” aspect to highlight Fengkai’s historical roots. From the communicative perspective, the original slogan does not explicitly mention the “Great Stone”, Fengkai’s massive rock formation, which is comparable in size and significance to Australia’s Ayers Rock.

Translation (2) emphasizes Asia’s largest monolithic rock, enhancing the slogan’s distinctiveness by drawing attention to this unique feature.

Translation (3) directly introduces “Ayers Rock” as a point of cultural reference, using augmentation to appeal to the familiarity that foreign tourists may have with Ayers Rock. All three translations use prepositional phrases, breaking away from the literal text to leverage eco-translatology’s principles, particularly those related to natural and cultural environments. This approach fosters resonance with international audiences by associating Fengkai’s natural and historical features with globally recognized concepts.

Slogan: 生态燕都 大美怀集 (Huaiji County)

Translations:

- (1). Eco-friendly Huaiji
- (2). Home of Cave Swiftlets

Analysis:

The original slogan highlights Huaiji’s ecological beauty and its significance as the “Swallow Capital”, referring specifically to the region’s reputation as a habitat for cave swiftlets. Translation (1) uses reduction to provide a concise, environmentally themed description, capturing the essence of Huaiji as a green destination. By summarizing the original message into “Eco-friendly Huaiji”, this translation keeps the slogan simple while resonating with eco-conscious tourists.

Translation (2) takes a more specific approach, focusing on Huaiji’s unique status as the inland habitat for cave swiftlets, whose presence indicates a pristine ecological environment. This translation emphasizes the communicative and cultural dimensions by referencing an ecological fact that reflects Huaiji’s natural beauty and uniqueness. The reduction method is used here as well, focusing on the “Swallow Capital” aspect to connect more directly with Huaiji’s defining ecological feature.

V. CONCLUSION

In the context of holistic tourism, the translation of tourism slogans plays a critical role in promoting a city’s brand internationally and attracting global tourists. Translating tourism slogans is not merely about direct conversion of the original text; it involves distilling and representing the region’s cultural identity, natural characteristics, and historical depth. This study applied the three-dimensional principles of eco-translatology—linguistic, cultural, and communicative dimensions—to analyze tourism slogans from select U.S. states, deriving insights that inform the translation of Zhaoqing’s representative tourism slogans into English.

Through the theoretical lens of eco-translatology, this paper explores translation strategies for Zhaoqing’s slogans, focusing on pragmatic and cultural adaptation to enhance their effectiveness in international promotion. Emphasis was placed on highlighting Zhaoqing’s unique resources through concise and memorable English slogans to attract foreign visitors. By flexibly applying reduction, augmentation, and cultural substitution techniques, the translations retain the distinct cultural essence of the region while aligning with the simplicity and clarity expected in English expressions. This approach minimizes cultural comprehension barriers and enhances communicative impact.

This research aims to strengthen the international reach of Zhaoqing’s tourism brand and offers a translation model for other tourism cities. In doing so, it contributes to the broader effort to elevate the recognition and appeal of China’s holistic tourism on a global scale.

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